

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF MANUSCRIPT SOURCES OF JADID LITERATURE

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Abstract. *The article examines the study of classical literature on the basis of originality, informing students about manuscript sources, preparing them as specialists, publishing classical sources on the basis of manuscripts, preparing the text of excellent scientific commentaries, as well as the fact that conducting new scientific and theoretical research in the field of source studies and textual studies is one of the most pressing issues today, it examines the work of Abdullah Avloni “Turkish Gulistan or Morality”, which promotes the style of confrontation, high spiritual values, children’s nature, love for the motherland, honesty and other human qualities, as a program to raise the spirituality of today’s young generation as well as issues such as the need to combine education and upbringing.*

Keywords: *classic, manuscript source, lithographic source, counter style, source studies, textual studies, Nasta’liq script, scientific commentaries, mufradot, murakkabot, transcription, conversion, transliteration, textological character.*

Today’s period, like all other spheres, requires raising the quality of education to a higher level. There are many methods and factors for the development of education: the introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the field, the effective use of modern pedagogical technologies of teaching, the continuous improvement of professional skills of teachers. We all know that in the process of education, it is gratifying that new and advanced experiences as well as interactive methods of teaching are being discovered and put into practice by skilled teachers. It is necessary to combine education and upbringing in the education of students. As noted by President Sh.M.Mirziyoev, “It is known that the upbringing of the younger generation has always been important and relevant. But in the 21st century we live in, this issue is really becoming a matter of life and death. “The more perfect the upbringing, the happier the people will live,” say the sages. In order for education to be perfect, there must be no gap in this issue”¹.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on May 24, 2017 No. PQ-2995 “On measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources” as well as during the visit of President Shavkat Mirziyoev to the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 23, 2017, the task was set to conduct research aimed at studying the sources of Uzbek classical literature, and first of all, to train qualified source and textual staff. According to the resolution, today’s era of globalization requires a high level of quality education, as well as in all areas.

¹Sh. M. Mirziyoev. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Book 1, “Uzbekistan”, 2017. -B. 504-505.

The methods that enter the educational process under the name of “interactive methods of teaching” allow the teacher to achieve high results in a short time. However, it should be noted that the delivery of certain theoretical information to the student in a short period of time, the formation of skills and competencies on the topic, as well as their monitoring and evaluation requires high pedagogical skills from the teacher. The teaching process should be organized in such a way that all students are actively involved in the lesson, that is, a certain part of the learning materials is studied independently by students (individually, in pairs or in groups), and then this information is discussed in detail. Independent works are done in the same way. The student should feel free during the lesson so that he or she can express his or her independent opinion.

In order to develop students’ skills of independent learning, it is planned to work on various sources related to the content of the topic, extensive use of textbooks, additional literature and Internet resources, independent work on manuscripts and lithographs, conversations on the topic, practical training².

The Uzbek literary criticism of the period of independence has developed the principle of describing new literary sources of classical poetry that have not been previously published, in particular, a broader view of the aspects of poetic genres related to life and human destiny, accurate assessment of the power and importance of art of artistic expression³.

It is impossible to talk about the development of the science of textual studies without a deep and scientific study of the text of classical works of art. Because the concept and history of literary text manuscript are one of the basic theoretical foundations of textology.

Valuable information about the rich scientific and spiritual heritage, literature and art of the Uzbek people is reflected in the manuscript sources. The study of classical literature on the basis of originality, informing students about manuscript sources, training them as specialists will increase the cultural and educational level in the higher education system. One of the most pressing issues today is the publication of classical sources on the basis of manuscripts, the preparation of critical texts with excellent scientific commentary, indicators, new scientific and theoretical research in the field of source studies and textual studies. To do this, high results can be achieved by working based on the style of interaction and experience working on the manuscript text. When applying the method of dialogue in the process of studying the history of the text, in particular, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following important features: 1) the sole purpose of the scholars is to work as a team with the intention of restoring the perfect text without errors; 2) letter-by-letter, word-for-word comparison of the text; 3) in order to eliminate errors, experts check the texts they have prepared by exchanging them with each other; 4) work on the text without deleting errors; 5) to establish the issuance of a special

²Sirojiddinov Sh. Literary Source Studies and Textual Studies.- T., 2018; Sirojiddinov Sh., Umarova S. Aspects of Uzbek textual criticism.-T .: Akademnashr, 2015; Sodikov K. Fundamentals of Textual Studies and Source Studies.-Tashkent: Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies, 2017. p. 216; Khakimov M. Dictionary of Oriental Source Studies.-T., 2013; Khabibullaev A. Literary Source Studies and Textual Studies. -Tashkent, 2000; T. Shermukhammedov., F. Abdullaev., L. Khalilov., A. Khalilov. Textbook. -T., 1994; F. Iskhakov. Ancient Uzbek language and writing. - T., 1995; S. Ashirboev., I. Azimov., M. Rakhmatov., A. Ghoziev. Ancient Uzbek language and writing practicum. - T., 2006.

³M.Asadov. Soqiynoma: history and poetics. – Tashkent: Tafakkur, 2020, p. 10.

permit by the Society of Textologists, if previously the teacher gave a written permission to teach a lesson on the restored reliable text⁴.

The scientifically based criteria and principles of studying the text of classical works of art that can be applied to research in this area have not yet been clearly developed. This, in turn, requires the development of an integrated system of text history research, which is the basis of both textual studies and literary-scientific analysis. It is no secret that in the upbringing of well-educated and mature young people, who are the future of the nation, special attention is paid to the education and upbringing, as well as the promotion of universal ideas put forward in the masterpieces of our classical literature. In particular, Abdullah Avloni's didactic work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality", which promotes high spiritual values, respect for parents, family, children's nature, love for the motherland, honesty, integrity, purity and many other beautiful human qualities, there is no doubt that it will be programmatic in raising its spirituality. In teaching students, the teacher is required to combine education and upbringing.

It is well known that the Uzbek-Turkish script based on the Arabic alphabet has been in use for thousands of years. In the standard curriculum and standard program of the field of study 5120100 – Bachelor's degree in Philology and Language Teaching (Uzbek), 36 hours are allocated for lectures, 36 hours for practical training, 50 hours for independent study on the subject of "Textology". The program covers the difference between the concept of text in textology and linguistics, history of Arabic writing, current problems of textual criticism, conversion, transcription, transliteration, the role of lexicography in understanding classical texts, reading lithographs and manuscripts in Nasta'liq script (Arabic script), reading and understanding the reformed alphabet of the early twentieth century, prose concise and complete interpretation of the text, classification of literary source, the ancient Uzbek writing, importance of title in manuscript, possibility of scientific index in classical text, types of manuscripts, scientific descriptive structures in catalogs, mufradot, murakkabot (complexity), spelling, other issues related to the ancient Uzbek writing, annotated text reading, textual studies and source studies. Texts in the old Uzbek script consist of manuscripts created before the years of 1929-1930, and in order to ensure that students can read the manuscripts freely, during the 6th semester, students must also complete the topics allocated for independent study.

Attempts to combine the field of philology with the field of source studies, which is the main field of activity of historians, led to the emergence of the term "literary source" in our country. After independence, the study of Oriental manuscripts, the rapid revival of manuscript sources, research and publication, the study of classical manuscripts also contributed to the rapid development of the field of textual studies. Manuscripts of works of ancient literature were transliterated and published in modern Uzbek. However, the lack of popularization of the long-standing experience in the study of the text of classical manuscripts has led to a complete ignorance of the scientific and artistic significance of published sources and their value as a

⁴N. Jabborov. Some comments on the history of the text and its genesis. // Proceedings of the international scientific-practical conference "Problems of textual criticism and source studies in Uzbek philology", dedicated to the 580th anniversary of the great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi. -Namangan, May 19-20, 2021. p. 10; Jabborov N. Uzbek textology and text criticism in it, the role of scientific and critical text terminology // Theoretical and source bases of studying Uzbek classical literature. Materials of the Republican scientific-practical conference. – Tashkent: Classic word, 2019. Page 9.

written monument due to ignorance of textual research methods. The lack of systematization of the tasks, classification, types and principles of publication in the field of textual studies creates certain difficulties for our linguists and literary critics working on the study of manuscripts. This made it necessary to increase the effectiveness of reforms in the spiritual and educational sphere, to raise the work in this direction to a qualitatively new level.

In philology, there is no single rule accepted by the majority in matters of working on a text. While source scholars focus more on the history, research, and description of the text, textual scholars pay more attention to the study of textual interpretation in addition to them. Therefore, source studies differ in that they belong to the field of historical and natural sciences, and textologists in the field of philology. In turn, there is still no consensus among textologists on the issues of artistic and linguistic study of texts.

Textual Studies conducts an imaginative study of all the advantages and disadvantages of a manuscript, from the textual features of the copy to the printed form. There are a number of methods of textual research, including analysis of textual differences, analysis of copying errors, identification of errors in the author's text, identification of text modifications, implementation of manuscript description, identification of additions and omissions, analysis of differences between manuscripts and lithographs, interrelationships between copies and relationship detection, textual character identification, text creation, and other similar methods.

It is well known that in the current context where the scope of information and knowledge is rapidly expanding, it is very difficult to convey all the information to students only during the course. Experience shows that in a modular system, a student can deepen his knowledge only if he is engaged independently and works tirelessly on himself. Students' basic knowledge, skills and abilities are formed only in the process of independent learning, the ability to act independently develops, and they develop an interest in creative work. Therefore, one of the main tasks is to plan students' independent learning on the basis of a modular system, to organize it and create all the necessary conditions for this, to teach manuscripts in the classroom, as well as to show ways of learning, orientation to independent learning⁵.

Independent work of the student is a systematic activity aimed at the acquisition of a certain part of the knowledge, skills and competencies defined in the science curriculum by the student outside the classroom on the basis of the advice and recommendations of the science teacher, assignments should be well thought out and goal-oriented, aimed at consolidating, deepening, expanding, and supplementing the knowledge students have acquired during the course. In determining the form and scope of independent work, the following should be taken into account: the stage of study; the nature of the science and the degree of difficulty in mastering it; provision of science with information sources; independent study of some topics with the help of additional literature; the degree to which students are able to work with manuscript sources and the like.

On the subject of "Textology" for the studying of the manuscript of Abdullah Avloni "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" it is allocated 4 hours in total, 2 hours of which are for practical work, and 2 hours for independent work. These types of study sessions are the most

⁵Khamidova M., Sulaymonova N. Ancient Uzbek script. –Tashkent, 2009; Azimov I., Ghoziev A. Independent work on the subject of the ancient Uzbek language and writing practicum. – Tashkent, 2010; Khamidov Z., Ubaydullaev A., Egamova Sh. Ancient Uzbek language and script (text of the lecture). - Tashkent, 2001.

important components of current supervision, as this work is done independently by the student throughout the semester. The development of practical and independent education is carried out in accordance with the plan on the basis of copying the manuscript written in **Nasta'liq script** (Arabic script) in accordance with all the rules of the ancient Uzbek script. Below is an example of a 2-hour practical work. At the end of the lesson, the homework and work to be done will be given. At the beginning of the lesson, the teacher gives students an overview of the topic of practical training and the work to be done during the lesson. Working on a manuscript text is not a simple copying, the process consists of the following:

Exercise 1. The manuscript text is selected, the group students are divided into 2 groups and the text given to each group is read first. This process is done independently and is read in front of the teacher. Words and sentences that are difficult to read in the text are done under the guidance of the teacher.

Group 1. Text 1.

عبدلله اولانى "توركى گلستان ياخود اخلاق" د ن
ياخشى خلقلار

ياخشى خلق: بىر قىسمى اوز نفسىمىزگە بىر قىسمى بىر بىرىمىزگە قارشى ایشلاتمىك اوچون كىركاي بولگان ياخشى خلقلار: فطانت، دىانت، اسلاميت، نظافت، غيرت، رياضت، قناعت، شجاعت، علم، صبر، حلم، اينتظام، مقياس نفس، وجدان، وطنى سويىمىك، حقانيت، نظر عبرت، عفت، حيا، ادراك و ذكا حفظ لسان اقتصاد، وفا، خوف و رجا، اطاعت، حق شناسلىك، خىر خواهلك، مونسلىك، صداقت، محبت و عفودور. منه: بو يازد بىغىمىز ياخشى خلقلار عقل و شرع شريفغه موافق الله تعالى هم بنده لار قاشيده مقبول معتبر دور. ايمدى بو ياخشى خلقلار نى قولگه آلك اوچون آنا، معلم استادلار بىمىز حىر تارلار بىنىنگ حكمتلى نصيحتلار بىنى جان قولاغى بىرله تىنگلاب دايم خاطرده توتماق، اخلاقى ياخشى كىشىلار برله الفت بولمىك، اخلاقى بوزوق يامان كىشىلار دن قاچماق لازم دور. بىزم شريعت اسلاميه ده «اخلاق حسنه» ياخشى خلقلار ايله خلقلانمىك هر نرسه گه عبرت كوزى ايله باقوب خلقىنى تواتمىك واجب دور. رسول اكرم نبى محترم ﷺ «اسلاميت ده بوزوقلىق بوق دور. بوزوقلىقى اوستىگه آلو هم بوقدور. اسلاميت ده اينگ معتبر كىشى لار ياخشى خلق اىگالار بىدور» دىمىشلار.

Group 2. Text 2.

عبدلله اولانى "توركى گلستان ياخود اخلاق" د ن
اخلاق

انسانلار بىنىنگ ياخشىلىكغە چاقىرگوچى يامانلىك دن قايتارگوچى بر علم دور. ياخشى خلق لار بىنىنگ ياخشىلىگىنى يامان خلق لار بىنىنگ يامانلىگىنى دليل و مثال لار ايله بيان قىلدورگان كتابنى اخلاق دىبلور. اخلاق علمىنى اوقوب بىلوب عمل قىلگان كىشى لار اوزى بىنىنگ كىم اىكانىن جناب حق نه اوچون خلق قىلگانىن بىر بوزيده نىمه ايش قىلمىك اوچون بورگانىن بىلور. بر كىشى اوزى دن خبردار بولماسه علم نى، عامانى، ياخشى كىشى لارنى، ياخشى نرسه لارنى، ياخشى ايشلارنى قدرىنى، قىمتىنى بىلماس. اوز عىبىنى بىلوب اقرار قىلىب تواتمىكغە سعى و كوشش قىلگان كىشى چىن بهادر و پهلوان كىشىدور رسول اكرم نبى محترم افند بىمىز ميزان ترازوسىگه قويدورگان عمل لار بىنىنگ اىچيده ياخشى خلق دن آغىر راغى بوقدور. مؤمن بنده ياخشى خلقى سببلى كوندوز لارى روزه توتوب عبادت قىلگان كىشى لار د رجه سىگه بىتار دىمىشلار.

Exercise 2. Students prepare a dictionary of words that are difficult for them to understand. In this case, special attention should be paid to the meaning of the word in the text.

Dictionary	Meaning
فطانت	
نظافت	
رياضت	
حلم	
مقياس نفس	

ادراك و ذكا	
حفظ لسان	
حوف و رجا	
مونسليک	
شريعنت اسلاميه	
حق شناسليک	
اخلاق حسنه	

Exercise 3. The text is copied in a notebook by pencil (pen) in accordance with the requirements of calligraphy (with attention to calligraphy).

Exercise 4. Some sentences in the text are written on the board by the students and the words in the sentence that are difficult to read and write are explained one by one.

Exercise 5. The text distinguishes between “good behavior” and “bad behavior” and analyzes it from today’s perspective. Students do this using the Venn diagram:

Exercise 6. The text in the ancient Uzbek script (Arabic) must be transliterated into the current Uzbek script.

Exercise 7. Read the given text, describe the prose and explain its meaning.

بیت

یاخشی برله یورسه هر کیم مقصودی حاصل بولور
یورسه نادانلا ر ایله بیر کون باریب قاتل بولور
کلاته لار قیلگان نصیحتتی کیچیکلا ر آلمسه
عاقبت خلقی بوزوق بیر بی ادب جاهل بولور

Homework: read and master the given text independently

عبدالله اولانی ”تورکی گلستان یاخود اخلاق“ دن

حفظ لسان

حفظ لسان د یب هر بیر ملت اوز انا تیل و ادبیاتینی ساقلاماکی ایتیلور.
هر بیر ملت نینگ دنیاده بارلیغین کورساتادورگان آینه حیاتی تیل و
ادبیاتیدور. ملی تیلنی یوقاتمک ملت نینگ روحینی یوقا تمکدور. هیهات!
بیز ترکستان لیلار ملی تیلنی ساقلامک بیر طرفده تورسون کوند ن کون
اونوتمک و یوقاتمکده دورمیز. تیلیمزنینگ یا رمیگه عربی، فارسی
اولانگانی کم لیک قیلوب بیر چیتیگه روس تیلینی هم یاپشورمکده
دورمیز. درست، بیزلارکه حکومتیمیز بولغان روس لسانینی بیلمک حیات
و سعادتیمیز اوچون آش و نان کبی کیراکلک نرسه دور. لیکن اوز بیرینده
ایشلاتمک و سوزلامک لازم دور. زغیر یاغی سالوب ماشکیچیری کبی
قیلوب آرالاش قورالاش قیلیمک تیلینینگ روحینی بوزادور. یا هو! بیزگه نه

بولدى؟ بابالاريميز بوليد ن چيقوب كيتدوك. «ياخشى قوشنىنگ ن آلگونچه
يامان اويىنگنى قيدير» ديميشلار. بابالاريميزگه ييتوشغان و ياراگان مقدس
تيل و ادبيات بيزگه هيچ كملك قيلماس. اوز اوييميزنى قيديرساك و
آختارساك يوقالغان لارنى هم تاپورمىز. «يوقالسە يوقالسون اوزى باشمىگه
تار ايدى» ديب يوروپا قالياغىنى كيوب كولگى بولمك زور عيب و
اوياتدور. پيغمبريمىز «ايرلارده جمال لسان و تيلدور» ديميشلار.

اي انا تيل! عزيز قدر دانيم

التفات رحيم رحمانيم

توغد يغم كوندن ايلادنگ الفت

اولگونيمچه آييلمه اى جانيم

مينگه علم و ادب سن اورگاتدينگ

چين اديب معلم شانيم

ملتنينگ روحىنى كونارگوچى سن

اينگ مقدس كرملى سلطانيم

عمومى مى تيلنى ساقلاماك ايله برابر خصوصى آغيز آراسيده گى تيلنى
هم ساقلاماك لازم دور. چونكه سوز انسان نينگ درجه و كمالينى، علم و
فضلىنى اولجاب كورساتدورگان ترازوسيدور. عقل صاحب لارى كيشى
نينگ دليده گى فكر و نيتى نى، علم و قوتىنى، قدر و قيمتى نى سوزلاگان
سوزيدن بيلورلار.....

List of recommended literature on the topic

1. Abdullaev F., Shermuhammedov T., Xalilov L., Xalilov A. Textbook.-Tashkent: Teacher, 1994.
2. Ashirboyev S., Azimov I. Rakhmatov M. and Goziyev A. Practicum of the Ancient Uzbek language and writing. T.: House of Creativity. 2006
3. Abdulla Avloni. Selected works. Volume 2.-Tashkent: Manaviyat, 2006.
4. Abdulla Avloni. Turkish gulistan or morality. -Tashkent: Teacher, 1992.

Assignments also serve for independent study of the topic. Depending on the specific nature of the subject, the level of knowledge and ability of the students, specific topics included

in the curriculum are given to students as homework for independent study. It requires key words and phrases that are the basis for the disclosure and analysis of the main content of the topic, attention to the questions that serve to systematically describe the topic, a clear indication of the main and additional literature and sources of information. The work on the independently mastered theme is defended at the department.

The main homework texts are manuscripts, and students should pay attention to the following when completing them:

- The text of the given manuscript is first read by the student independently. This process is done independently and is read in front of the teacher.
- Words and sentences in the text that are difficult to read are read under the guidance of the teacher;
- The student prepares a dictionary of words that are difficult for him to read and understand, based on textbooks and additional literature at home. In this case, the emphasis should be on the meaning of the word in the text;
- The text in Arabic will be translated into the current Uzbek script;
- The text is also compared with the text in Cyrillic and Latin scripts;
- The student must know the scientific significance of the manuscript in the study of classical texts, the type of letter in which the manuscript was written;
- The most important result is that the text is read independently by students, perceived by each student, accepted in a unique way, draws unique conclusions.

One of the priorities in the effective organization of independent work of students is a systematic approach, coordination and integration of all stages, the establishment of strict control over the work, the improvement of its organization and control mechanisms. The fact that the manuscript is read independently by students, that each student understands it, that it is accepted in a unique way, that he or she draws unique conclusions is a very important result in teaching science.

The value of working as a group in the study of a manuscript is so valuable that it requires teamwork - a number of students and teachers working together in a scientific collaboration. Naturally, scientific cooperation is highly effective, especially in the field of textual studies. In this regard, one of the priorities of textual studies is the study of the manuscript text and its history, its application to the process of making perfect and reliable editions of classical literature. This requires a high level of skill from the teacher.

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